

Final dataset delivery

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE DN.13 - SUMMER

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	13/12/2025	First draft	R.Bosio(POLITO)
0.5			
0.9			
1	20/12/2025	Final version	R.Bosio(POLITO)

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Dataset

The [SUMMER digital platform](#) serves as the centralized data repository of the Flagship, integrating both the outputs and datasets generated throughout the project. All information is organized into macro-categories and can be freely browsed by users through the platform interface. While most datasets are openly accessible, selected data may be temporarily shielded or restricted when linked to ongoing scientific publications or subject to confidentiality constraints.

Structure of the dataset

The dataset was organized into macro-categories relating to the main topics of the individual Research Modules:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RM1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Glaciers ○ Monitoring ○ Snow Water Equivalent • RM2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy Resources ○ Solar Panel • RM3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Landslides • RM4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Watershed Framework ○ Infrastructures ○ Hydraulic Resources 	
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Dataset Use and Explanation

The SUMMER digital platform functions as the centralized data hub of the Flagship, aggregating both project outputs and the datasets produced across its various research activities. All resources are organized into thematic macro-categories, each containing a coherent set of datasets aligned with its specific domain (e.g., climate, hydrology, energy, remote sensing, etc.). The catalogue of datasets and data files is continuously updated as new measurements, models, and results become available, ensuring the platform remains current throughout and beyond the project lifecycle.

From a user perspective, the platform offers an intuitive data exploration workflow: by selecting a layer, users gain access to the underlying dataset and can interact with it directly within the platform environment, inspecting values, visualizing patterns, and retrieving detailed metadata and contextual information. While most datasets are openly accessible for consultation, some may be temporarily restricted or partially masked when associated with ongoing scientific publications or subject to confidentiality and dissemination constraints.

In addition to on-platform exploration, authenticated users are granted the ability to download available datasets for further offline analysis, enabling broader scientific reuse, didactic integration, and knowledge transfer within the SUMMER community and beyond.

Figure 1 – Platform view. Example of Dataset view and Download.

List of the Actual Layers

- Frane
 - Catalogo Frane Valle Orco
 - Delineazione Frane – marker (computer vision)
 - Delineazione Frane – poligono (computer vision)
 - Modello Suscettibilità Frane – VDA (2003-2022)
 - Modello Suscettibilità Frane – VDA (2021-2040)
- Gestione Invasi
 - Modello di Ottimizzazione Invasi Valle Orco
- Ghiacciai
 - 1988
 - 2006
 - 2015
 - 2018
 - Tracce Rilievi Geofisici Rutor (2018)
- Infrastrutture
 - Tralicci Alta Tensione Valle Orco
- Monitoraggio
 - Rete Monitoraggio ARPA – Valle Orco
 - Rete Monitoraggio NODES
- Risorse Energetiche
 - Delineazione Pannelli Fotovoltaici
 - Delimitazione tetti e potenziale fotovoltaico
 - Potenziale Idroelettrico – raggio 1Km
 - Potenziale Idroelettrico – raggio 2.5Km
 - Potenziale Idroelettrico – raggio 5Km
 - Radiazione Solare Media Mensile Edifici
 - REC Frassinetto
- Risorse Idriche
 - CDP – Valle Orco
 - Prese Superficiali Valle Orco
 - Restituzioni Valle Orco
 - Rete Interconnessione Prese-Restituzioni
- Snow Water Equivalent
 - Average Monthly SWE, 2023-01

- Average Monthly SWE, 2023-02
- Average Monthly SWE, 2023-03
- Average Monthly SWE, 2023-04
- Average Monthly SWE, 2023-05
- Average Monthly SWE, 2023-06
- Average Monthly SWE, 2023-07
- Average Monthly SWE, 2023-08
- Average Monthly SWE, 2023-09
- Average Monthly SWE, 2023-10
- Average Monthly SWE, 2023-11
- Average Monthly SWE, 2023-12